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An intrinsic link between DNA damage and Xist evidenced through deletion mutants of Xist defective in H2AX induction.

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One deletion mutant of Xist was completely defective in H2AX induction. Transcriptome analysis indicated H2AX induction, and thus the relay of DNA damage signaling, was a basic and major function of Xist in the human cell.